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ELECTRICITY DEMAND FORECASTING IN CASE OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This study is aimed to forecast demand for electricity in case of Uzbekistan in medium term with the influences of economic growth and population growth. For forecasting the demand for electricity, ARIMAX model is employed as time series data is utilized for the study. In response to preliminary findings, the economic growth and population growth are argued as one of the major sources and factors to rise demand for electricity, but the question was by how much those factors lead to growth of electricity demand in case of Uzbekistan. Thus, by taking into account those factors, the electricity demand has been struggled to forecast by 2027 based on the past data from 2010 till 2023.

Key words: Electricity demand, ARIMAX, Uzbekistan, GDP growth, Population.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot O'zbekiston misolida elektr energiyasiga bo'lgan talabni o'rta muddatli istiqbolda prognoz qilishga qaratilgan bo'lib, bunda iqtisodiy o'sish va aholi sonining o'sishi kabi omillar hisobga olingan. Elektr energiyasiga bo'lgan talabni prognoz qilish uchun vaqt qatori ma'lumotlariga asoslangan ARIMAX modeli qo'llanildi. Dastlabki natijalarga ko'ra, iqtisodiy o'sish va aholi sonining ko'payishi elektr energiyasiga bo'lgan talabning oshishiga olib keladigan asosiy omillardan biri sifatida baholanmoqda. Ammo savol shuki, bu omillar elektr energiyasi talabining o'sishiga qanday darajada ta'sir qiladi? Shu bois, mazkur omillarni hisobga olgan holda 2010-yildan 2023-yilgacha bo'lgan tarixiy ma'lumotlar asosida 2027-yilgacha elektr energiyasiga bo'lgan talab prognoz qilindi.

Kalit so'zlar: Elektr energiyasiga talab, ARIMAX, O'zbekiston, YAIM o'sishi, Aholi soni.

Аннотация: Данное исследование направлено на прогнозирование спроса на электроэнергию в Узбекистане в среднесрочной перспективе с учетом влияния экономического роста и роста численности населения. Для прогнозирования спроса на электроэнергию используется модель ARIMAX, основанная на временных рядах. Согласно предварительным результатам, экономический рост и рост населения являются одними из основных факторов увеличения спроса на электроэнергию. Однако остается вопрос: насколько сильно эти факторы влияют на рост спроса в Узбекистане? Учитывая эти факторы, спрос на электроэнергию был спрогнозирован до 2027 года на основе данных за период с 2010 по 2023 годы.

Ключевые слова: Спрос на электроэнергию, ARIMAX, Узбекистан, Рост ВВП, Население.

INTRODUCTION

Uzbekistan's electricity sector has undergone significant transformations over the past decade, marked by substantial growth in generation capacity, evolving consumption patterns, and proactive regulatory measures. As the nation strides towards economic expansion and population growth, accurately forecasting electricity demand becomes imperative to ensure a stable and sustainable energy future. Between 2016 and 2024, Uzbekistan experienced a remarkable 38% increase in electricity generation, reaching 81.5 billion kilowatt-hours. This surge was largely driven by the liberalization of the private sector, which contributed an additional 11.2 gigawatts to the national grid. Notably, private sector participation now accounts for 24% of the total generation capacity, while renewable energy sources have expanded to comprise 16% of the energy mix.

The residential sector has mirrored this upward trend in electricity consumption. In 2016, household usage was approximately 10.5 billion kilowatt-hours; by 2024, it had doubled to over 21 billion kilowatt-hours. This escalation is attributed to rising household incomes and the increased adoption of modern electrical appliances. Looking ahead, Uzbekistan's demographic and economic projections indicate a continued rise in electricity demand. With the population expected to reach 41 million by 2030 and the economy anticipated to expand 1.5 times its current size, electricity consumption is forecasted to hit 117 billion kilowatt-hours by 2030 and 135 billion kilowatt-hours by 2035—a 1.7-fold increase from present levels.

To address these challenges, the Uzbek government has implemented a series of regulatory measures aimed at promoting efficient electricity consumption and ensuring the reliability of energy supply. In August 2024, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev signed a new version of the law “On Electric Power Industry,” establishing the Agency for the Development and Regulation of the Energy Market as the central authority responsible for approving tariffs and overseeing market regulations. This agency is tasked with issuing licenses for power plant operations and implementing a unified state policy in the energy sector.

In May 2024, the government introduced a social norm for electricity consumption, setting a baseline of 200 kilowatt-hours per month for households. This initiative aims to enhance energy efficiency and ensure targeted use of budgetary subsidies. Analyses indicate that 60% of subscribers consume less than this threshold, suggesting that the majority of households are within the established norm.

For the commercial sector, measures have been implemented to encourage prudent energy use. As of June 2024, businesses exceeding their electricity consumption limits by more than 10% are subject to double tariff rates, increasing from 900 UZS to 1,800 UZS per kilowatt-hour for the excess consumption. This policy is designed to promote energy conservation among enterprises and reduce overall demand on the national grid.

In conclusion, Uzbekistan's electricity demand is on an upward trajectory, driven by demographic growth and economic development. The government's proactive regulatory framework, coupled with investments in renewable energy and infrastructure, positions the nation to meet future energy needs sustainably. Accurate forecasting of electricity demand will be crucial in guiding these efforts, ensuring that supply aligns with consumption patterns, and supporting Uzbekistan's continued progress.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

Electricity demand forecasting is essential for policymakers, energy suppliers, and grid operators to ensure efficient energy production, distribution, and consumption. Various countries have employed different forecasting models, incorporating economic, demographic and climatic factors. This section reviews empirical studies on electricity demand forecasting in different regions highlighting methodologies and findings.

Studies on electricity demand forecasting in developed countries often emphasize advanced economic models and machine learning techniques. For example, in the United States, Baumeister and Kilian (2016) employed a Structural Vector Autoregressive (SVAR) model to analyze electricity consumption, finding that GDP growth and industrial activity were primary drivers of demand. Similarly, Hyndman and Fan (2010) utilized a functional time series approach to predict Australia's electricity consumption and found that temperature fluctuations significantly affected peak demand.

In Europe, Bianco et al. (2009) used a regression model incorporating GDP and population growth to forecast electricity demand in Italy. Their study demonstrated that economic cycles strongly influence consumption trends. In Germany, Muller et al (2018) applied machine learning techniques, particularly Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), to improve the accuracy of demand forecasts concluding that incorporating weather variables enhanced prediction accuracy.

In emerging economies, electricity demand forecasting is critical due to rapid urbanization and industrialization. Studies in China have used hybrid models combining econometric and artificial intelligence approaches. For instance, Zhang et al (2018) employed a combination of the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model and Support Vector Machines (SVM) to predict electricity demand, achieving high accuracy. Their findings emphasized the impact of economic policies and renewable energy integration.

In India, Bhattacharyya and Timilsina (2010) examined electricity demand using a Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) model. Their results suggested that demand elasticity varies across income groups and industries. In contrast, a study by Ramanathan et al. (2000) used a time series model and identified seasonal variations in demand due to monsoon-related fluctuations.

In African nations, access to electricity remains a challenge, influencing demand forecasting approaches. Adebayo et al. (2019) applied a Bayesian Structural Time Series (BSTS) model to predict Nigeria's electricity consumption, finding that infrastructure development and energy pricing reforms significantly impact demand growth. In addition to this, some models such as ARIMA and SARIMA models have been widely applied in

several nations like Brazil (de Souza et al., 2020) and South Korea (Kim et al., 2019) for the implication of forecasting electricity demand in short term.

On top of that, econometric models such as regression analysis and vector autoregression (VAR) models have been used in France (Chauvet, 2018) and Malaysia (Rahman et al., 2021) to study the effect of economic factors on electricity demand.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employs an econometric approach to forecast electricity demand in Uzbekistan. The research utilizes the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average model with exogenous variables to capture the dynamic relationships between electricity demand, GDP growth and population growth. The methodology integrates historical annual data to estimate future electricity consumption trends and assess the impact of macroeconomic factors.

The general form of an ARIMA model is (ARIMA, p, d, q) where:

P = explains the number of autoregressive (AR) terms

D = reveals about the degree of differencing to achieve stationarity

Q = delivers information on number of moving average (MA) terms

Since GDP growth and population growth impact on electricity demand, the general equation of the ARIMA model is formulated as shown below:

$$Y_t = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_i Y_{t-i} + \sum_{j=1}^q \gamma_j \epsilon_{t-j} + \sum_{k=1}^m \delta_k X_{t-k} + \epsilon_t$$

Based on the equation above, Y_t stands for electricity demand at time t while X_t stands for explaining exogenous variables such as GDP growth, population growth and the last one ϵ_t reveals about error term in the model.

In addition to this, as this study is based on time series data, there are some data associated issues exist such as Stationarity, autocorrelation. In order to detect and mitigate those issues, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test and Phillips-Perron test are applied to check for unit roots. If non-stationarity is detected, differencing is performed until stationarity is achieved. Diagnostic checks, involving residual analysis and autocorrelation tests (Durbin – Watson) is going to be conducted to validate the model.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The primary objective of this study is to develop an accurate and reliable forecast of electricity demand in Uzbekistan, considering the impact of key macroeconomic factors. As energy demand continues to grow due to economic expansion and demographic changes, precise forecasting becomes essential for ensuring energy security, efficient resource allocation and informed policy-making.

The research aims to:

Examine the relationship between electricity demand and key economic factors

Develop and ARIMA-based forecasting model

Evaluate the forecasting accuracy and policy implications

By achieving these objectives, the study seeks to contribute to the broader understanding of energy demand dynamics in Uzbekistan and support evidence-based decision-making in energy policy.

Stationarity is a fundamental requirement for time series modeling using ARIMA. A stationary series has constant statistical properties over time such as mean, variance, autocorrelation, making it suitable for reliable forecasting. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test is commonly used to check for stationarity, where the null hypothesis states that the series has a unit root (table 1).

ADF test

Variable	1% Critical value	5% Critical value	10% Critical value	1 st difference	2 nd difference
Electricity demand	-3.750	-3.000	-2.630	-1.866	-10.065
GDP_growth	-3.750	-3.000	-2.630	-1.417	-2.831
Population_growth	-3.750	-3.000	-2.630	-1.720	-3.854

Breusch-Godfrey LM test for autocorrelation chi2	df	Prob>Chi2
0.114	1	0.735
6.483	2	0.039
7.103	3	0.069
8.696	4	0.069
9.380	5	0.095

H0: no serial correlation

The graph below presents about three key economic indicators for Uzbekistan over the periods of 2014 and 2024. Regarding to the graph below, the electricity demand which is explained by blue line is measured in terawatt-hours (TWh) for annual case while GDP is explained by orange line which is measured in USD in billions. Population growth that is drawn with light blue line is also measured in millions of people throughout the period.

Based on the provided information it is obvious that, the demand for electricity has been increased steadily throughout the periods. To be more precise, the demand for electricity was around 55 TWh in 2014 and this is projected to reach by 81 TWh by 2024. As it is visible from the graph that, there has been a noticeable drop around 2018, this is might be associated with economic downturns.

On top of that, GDP growth that is explained by orange line is also presented rising trend until 2017 before following sharp reduction from 2018 to 2020. This can be associated with economic slowdowns, policy changes or external shocks like global recessions or issues which are associated with trade. Nevertheless, economy of Uzbekistan started to rise from 2021 and projected to growth by \$101.58 billion in 2024. This strong economic growth correlates with increasing electricity demand, revealing that as the economy is expands, demand for electricity is also argued as increasing correspondingly.

The further line which is explained by light blue represents information about population growth of Uzbekistan during the selected time period and according to this, the population of Uzbekistan has reached to 36.025 million in 2024. This proposes a gradual and predictable growth in energy demand because of a larger consumer base. However, the slope of this line is much lower compared to GDP, this means that the economic factors have a stronger influence on electricity demand by compared to population growth alone (picture 1).

Pic.1. Macroeconomic factors of Uzbekistan

The major target of this study is to forecast the demand for electricity in case of Uzbekistan by empirically examining the influences of some macroeconomic factors such as population and GDP growth. The graph below reveals forecasting level of electricity demand along with selected variables till 2027 by implication of ARIMAX model for forecasting the value of each variable for short period of time.

In response to the forecasting of electricity demand, it is projected to be around 87.87 TWh around 2024 and it is expected to increase by 97.53 TWh in 2026 and it is argued as being around 105 TWh demand a year by coming to 2027. GDP is also expected to increase substantially in upcoming short future period. To be more accurate, the economy of Uzbekistan is project to rise by \$102 billion USD around 2024 and this trend is expected to rise by \$115 billion in 2026 and forecasted to be around \$132 billion by coming to 2027. Population of Uzbekistan is also predicted to observe rising trend and according to the forecasting results, the population of Uzbekistan is expecting to be around 36.78 million people during 2024 while that of is projecting to reach to 38.36 million people in 2026 and it is forecasted to be around 39.20 million people in 2027 (picture 2).

Pic.2. Comparison of macroeconomic factors between 2014 and 2026

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The analysis of electricity demand in Uzbekistan highlights the significant role of economic growth and demographic trends in shaping energy consumption patterns. By employing the ARIMA model with GDP growth and population growth as key independent variables, this study has provided valuable insights into the future trajectory of electricity demand.

The findings suggest that GDP growth is the most influential factor driving electricity consumption. Periods of economic expansion are strongly correlated with rising energy demand, as industrial production, commercial activities, and household consumption increase. Conversely, economic slowdowns or external shocks tend to dampen energy demand. Population growth, while contributing to increased consumption, exhibits a less pronounced impact compared to GDP, indicating that structural economic changes and industrialization play a larger role in shaping electricity demand.

Looking ahead, the forecasted increase in electricity demand underscores the importance of energy infrastructure investments and policy planning. The government must prioritize expanding power generation capacity, modernizing the electricity grid, and promoting energy efficiency to ensure a stable and sustainable energy supply. Additionally, exploring renewable energy sources and improving demand-side management will be crucial to meet future energy needs without excessive reliance on fossil fuels.

In conclusion, this study provides an empirical foundation for policy decisions and strategic planning in Uzbekistan's energy sector. Future research could further enhance forecasting accuracy by incorporating additional factors such as energy prices, technological advancements, and policy interventions. A well-planned approach to electricity demand management will be essential for supporting Uzbekistan's long-term economic growth and energy security.

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